

Enhancing 5G V-RAN Reliability via Reactive CU-UP Scaling

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Abstract—The 5th generation and beyond of cellular networks (5G & B5G) adopted a cloud-based architecture, representing a significant evolution compared to monolithic approaches of previous generations. This transformation has even been devised for the Radio Access Network (RAN), with the Cloud-RAN (C-RAN), and its virtualized version the Virtual RAN (V-RAN) as crucial and key components. RAN cloudification has added up to the flexibility, reduced deployment and operational costs for the network operators. The high-speed demands, vast volumes of data, and the low latency response requirements of future applications (e.g. V2X, IoT, URLLC, and others) create significant stress on some V-RAN components. In the V-RAN architecture, the CU-UP is highlighted as the datapath bottleneck of the V-RAN under high traffic loads. This paper aims to enhance the reliability of 5G V-RAN by addressing the bottleneck issues of CU-UP by developing a controller that performs reactive horizontal scaling of the CU-UP component. The scaling mechanism is driven by an algorithm that estimates CPU usage based on a Linear Regression model, based on the rate of incoming packets, with the goal to increase the overall 5G network performance delivered to the end users. Using real-world traffic patterns, we tested the proposed scaling mechanism, conducting the experiments in a non-simulated real-world testbeds exposing our system to dynamic conditions. Our findings highlight the importance of adapting such a scaling mechanism to ensure the robust reliability of the 5G V-RAN.

Index Terms—5G V-RAN, CU-UP scaling, 5G Reliability

I. INTRODUCTION

5G networks have introduced several innovations in terms of functionalities and features that add up to the flexibility for deployment and management of the network. One of the main innovations of beyond-5G networks (B5G) over their predecessors is the introduction of component disaggregation at both the 5G Core Network (5GCN) and the Radio Access Networks (RAN). Adopting a Service Based Architecture (SBA) for the 5GCN has been realized by converting each component into a Virtualized Network Function (VNF). Similarly, disaggregation for the RAN has been introduced with its functional separation into smaller sub-components with different responsibilities and functionality, allowing parts of the stack to be instantiated as VNFs.

Virtualizing the network has many benefits for the operators, as it adds up to the flexibility for deployment and

network maintenance, by decoupling the hardware resources from the actual traffic forwarding functions. Virtualization also allows the integration of methods intended for high availability of the infrastructure, such as scaling a network function, that have been previously used with success only for cloud-based services, unrelated to the operation of the network. The incorporation of such methods can offer higher performance benefits, and can enhance the reliability by performing scaling to the bottleneck component. Although the integration of scaling is well addressed for the 5GCN, for both Control Plane (CP) and User Plane (UP) functions, there is yet not much work being done to address similar issues for the Virtual RAN (V-RAN). In this work, we develop a scaling mechanism for the UP of the virtual 5G RAN, namely the Central Unit UP function (CU-UP).

In a monolithic 5G RAN, a single and unified entity integrates both the BaseBand Unit (BBU), responsible for handling the digital processing functionality and baseband functions, and the Remote Radio Unit (RRU), responsible for transmitting and receiving wireless signals. In contrast, Cloud-based RAN (C-RAN) transformed the 5G base station into a disaggregated cloud-based scheme based on a functional split of their protocols into the Central Unit (CU), the Distributed Unit (DU) and the Remote Unit (RU). The CU entity hosts the network layer functionality; in contrast, the DU is responsible for the Data Link Layer, and the RU is responsible for the physical layer and transmission over the air. The CU can also be disaggregated to the CU-Control Plane (CU-CP) and the CU-User Plane (CU-UP), separating the procedural functionality of the CU. The CU-UP is responsible for managing Service Data Adaptation Protocol (SDAP) marking, Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP) ciphering, packet switching/routing, header compression, and traffic management from multiple DUs. These tasks can create significant bottlenecks in network operation [1], especially under high load, as the high volume of processed packets may impact the reliability of the CU-UP. Through the deployment of a virtualized version of C-RAN (aka V-RAN), opportunities in the 5G management and overall flexibility for deployment are created. Considering that horizontal scaling is among the most effective methods for addressing potential bottlenecks in cloud environments [2], this paper aims to design a 5G system that facilitates reactive and dynamic horizontal scaling of the CU-UP component.

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Putting everything together, the main contributions of this paper are the following:

- To design and implement a dynamic horizontal scaling mechanism for the 5G V-RAN CU-UP component, validating using real-world traffic in a testbed environment.
- To enhance the reliability of 5G V-RAN by addressing the bottleneck issues of CU-UP.
- To provide a proof-of-concept on the horizontal scaling mechanism for the RAN.

II. RELATED WORK

As mentioned in Section I, the purpose of this work is to enhance the reliability of 5G V-RAN deployments by design a 5G system that supports a dynamic scaling mechanism for the CU-UP. In this section, we present the related literature with works that analyze, design, and implement scaling solutions to solve dependability issues in cloud and 5G networks.

Significant research has been conducted on VNF scaling, as this network capability enhances both the flexibility and scalability of networks. Two primary scaling strategies have been adopted: reactive scaling, which is triggered by the overutilization of node components [3], and proactive scaling, where scaling decisions are made in advance based on predictions of the network’s future state, often leveraging Machine Learning models such as ARIMA, XGBoost, and LSTM as seen in [4] and [5].

Based on these approaches, paper [6], presents a practical application of dynamic scaling of 5GCN components. The authors propose a dynamic AI-based scaling mechanism for the AMF in 5GCN, performing horizontal scaling based on connected UEs, active AMFs, and resource allocation. A Wavenet DNN is trained on real-world data to classify system states and determine scaling decisions. Authors in [7] present a machine-learning based algorithm to perform dynamic scaling and traffic forecasting scheme especially designed for 5G Open Radio Access Networks (O-RAN), aiming to enhance the reliability of the network. Each O-RAN component is depicted as a VNF, ML models (ARIMA and LSTM) are used for traffic forecasting and a Multi-Level Perceptron (MLP) is used for scaling decisions. The authors evaluate the proposed mechanism with real-world data traffic in a simulated environment, highlighting the potential of ML to enhance the 5G-RAN reliability. In [8], a mechanism for the dynamic management of 5GCN functions, with focus on the UPF scaling, is demonstrated, based on real-time monitoring of the node CPU usage. This work predicts network congestion, ensures better network performance and offers valuable techniques to manage the resource allocation of a 5G network. These methodologies can be applied in the 5G-V-RAN to improve the reliability of the CU-UP component.

Focusing more on the RAN part, work [9] demonstrates an ML-Driven dynamic scaling approach to enhance the reliability of a 5G-RAN. Four ML models were tested to predict the network load using a real-world dataset, and according to the predicted results a proactive scaling mechanism is triggered in order to scale vertically either the resources of the monolithic gNB or horizontally the instances of the UPF.

Work in [1] is quite similar to the concept of this specific manuscript but strongly differentiates in terms of the given solution. The authors recognize that the CU-UP is the bottleneck of the 5G-RAN UP. The proposed solution leverages eBPF (extended Berkeley Packet Filter) and XDP (eXpress Data Path) to bypass the kernel space and to enhance packet processing performance, meeting the high bandwidth and low latency demands of 5G deployments. The proposed scaling method does not focus on the CU-UP scaling but instead in offloading CPU intensive procedures to specialized hardware.

Contrary to all existing related works, we progress beyond the existing state-of-the-art by designing an automatic scaling mechanism for the disaggregated RAN. In this paper, we present the implementation and the outcomes of a 5G system that supports a dynamic horizontal scaling mechanism of the CU-UP component based on its CPU Usage, which reflects the incoming data traffic to it, using real-world environment and traffic pattern to conduct our experiments. This scaling process allows us to perform load-balancing of the traffic among multiple CU-UP instances to optimize the network operation, especially under heavy load. It is worth mentioning that the solution is also aligning with existing O-RAN architectures, that further define the split of the underlying components to O-DU and O-RU. The stress under which the CU-UP functions are placed remains the same, regardless of further splits that take place on the stack.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND ENVIRONMENT SETUP

In this section, we provide a detailed overview of the key components and system configuration for our proposed system architecture that supports reactive scaling of the CU-UP. Subsequently, we present our experimentation environment and configuration. For our architecture, we build on top of the 5G V-RAN network stack, supporting the F1 and E1 Split as described in [10]. In this architecture, the CU-CP includes the PDCP and RRC, the CU-UP is responsible for the PDCP and SDAP, and the DU includes the RLC and below layers.

Fig. 1: Reactive scaling V-RAN system architecture

A. System Architecture

The proposed 5G system architecture is based on a basic 5G Core Network, which includes the Network Repository Function (NRF), the User Data Repository (UDR), the Unified Data Management (UDM), the Authentication Server Function (AUSF), the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF), the Session Management Function (SMF), and a software-based User Plane Function (UPF) component. For

the 5G RAN deployment, we extend the fully disaggregated RAN that consists of the following components: a CU-CP, multiple CU-UPs, DUs and UEs as depicted in Figure 1. A controller is employed to reactively scale out or in the CU-UP instances according to their estimated CPU usage. First, the controller receives the number of packets transmitted by each CU-UP, over their F1-U interfaces. The number of the incoming packets received per CU-UP is aggregated, and the controller estimates the total CPU Usage per CU-UP based on a Linear Regression (LR) model. LR was chosen as during the experimental phase with the tested CU-UP implementation, an almost linear relationship was observed between the CPU usage and the number of packets processed. Additionally, LR is computationally efficient, making it a suitable choice for a time-critical scaling controller, such as the one developed in this work. The controller checks if the estimated CPU usage of any CU-UP instance is greater than a predefined threshold, and if the total number of instances is below a predefined limit, it instructs the system to scale out by deploying a new instance. Regarding the scale-in strategy, if the CPU usage of a CU-UP instance is below a predefined threshold and the number of instances is above the minimum limit, the algorithm searches for another CU-UP instance with underutilized CPU usage. Subsequently, it predicts the CPU usage of the merged traffic using the LR model. If the predicted CPU usage remains within acceptable limits, the controller scales in by terminating the underutilized CU-UP instance and redistributes traffic to the remaining instances. The functionality of the controller is detailed in Algorithm 1.

B. Experimental Setup

In order to evaluate our proposed system under real-world settings, we employ the NITOS testbed, which is the Greek node of the SLICES-RI [11], located in University of Thessaly, Greece. NITOS is an open-access infrastructure that provides a controlled and powerful environment to deploy 5G networks, highlighting the real-world applicability of our system. To deploy a 5G V-RAN network in the real world, we created a cloud-based environment using Kubernetes, an open-source container orchestration platform that automates the deployment and management of containerized applications. The proposed 5G network deployment is based on the OpenAirInterface (OAI) platform, which provides a software-based implementation of a cloud-native 5GCN (NRF, UDR, UDM, AUSF, AMF, SMF, UPF) and V-RAN (CU-CP, CU-UP, DU, UE) [12]. It is important to mention that the radio link between each UE and DU is not established over the air; instead, we used the rfsimulator to simulate a real Radio Frequency (RF) board. We opted to simulate real-world channel conditions using a model with Additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN). The choice of the rfsimulator is selected as we need to stress the CU-UP component, by injecting as much traffic as possible to it. Nevertheless, the proposed solution is fully compatible with traditional RF boards.

To investigate the reliability of the CU-UP we overload it with traffic. Experiment findings from our system under test

revealed that the maximum UDP downlink (DL) throughput achieved between a DU and UEs when scheduled on the same host was approximately 160 Mbps. When additional DUs were assigned to a single CU-UP, we observed that the CU-UP could not handle DL traffic exceeding 300 Mbps achieving CPU utilization over 95%. Using three DUs creates enough traffic to test the limits of the CU-UP and validate the effectiveness of the scaling mechanism. In order to support complete resource allocation and render the CU-UP the single congestion point across the datapath, we assign one UPF per DU. This is accomplished by assigning the UPFs to different network slices. We use a predefined UE to CU-UP assignment, based on the network slicing that we apply.

Algorithm 1 Reactive CU-UP Scaling Based on CPU Usage

Require: Upper_CPU_Threshold, Lower_CPU_Threshold

Require: Min_Instances, Max_Instances

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1: Definition:  $in\_traf(CU-UP[i])$  returns the total incoming traffic (in
   packets) handled by CU-UP instance  $i$ 
2: Initialize: Load Linear Regression (LR) model
3: while true do
4:   Retrieve packet counts from the API for each CU-UP instance
5:   for all CU-UP instance  $i$  do
6:     Predict  $CPU\_Usage[i] \leftarrow LR(Packets[i])$ 
7:   end for
8:   Check Scaling Up Conditions:
9:   for all CU-UP instance  $i$  do
10:    if  $CPU\_Usage[i] > Upper\_CPU\_Threshold$ 
11:      and  $Total\_Instances < Max\_Instances$  then
12:        Deploy a new CU-UP instance
13:        Reassign fairly traffic among active CU-UP instances
14:      break
15:    end if
16:  end for
17:  Check Scaling Down Conditions:
18:  for all CU-UP instance  $i$  do
19:    if  $CPU\_Usage[i] < Lower\_CPU\_Threshold$ 
20:      and  $Total\_Instances > Min\_Instances$  then
21:         $j \leftarrow Select$  CU-UP instance satisfying
22:         $CPU\_Usage[j] < Lower\_CPU\_Threshold$ 
23:         $tot\_in\_traffic \leftarrow in\_traf(CU-UP[i]) + in\_traf(CU-UP[j])$ 
24:         $pred\_cpu \leftarrow LR(tot\_in\_traffic)$ 
25:        if  $pred\_cpu \leq Upper\_CPU\_Threshold$  then
26:          Terminate CU-UP instance  $i$ 
27:          Reassign fairly traffic among active CU-UP instances
28:        break
29:      end if
30:    end if
31:  end for
32:  Wait for the next monitoring interval
33: end while

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In the subsequent design phase, we determined the number of nodes required for deploying the components and specified their assignments. To achieve an optimal configuration, we carefully selected and assigned the components to the nodes as follows: A node was chosen to be scheduled with all the CP entities of the 5G network (NRF, UDR, UDM, AUSF, AMF, SMF and CU-CP). These entities do not demand significant computational resources but are instead latency-sensitive. Two additional nodes were used, for a potential CU-UP deployment. Three nodes also having the same latency ($\approx 0.7ms$) to the CU-UPs nodes were selected in order to deploy the three UPFs. Additionally, three nodes were selected to deploy the three pairs of DUs and UEs, which

require high computational resources and have similar latency to the CU-UPs ($\approx 0.5ms$). Table I illustrates this assignment.

C. Controller & Scaling Implementation

Since the functionality of CU-UP is to forward packets to/from the UPF and from/to the DU after the encapsulation or decapsulation with the respective headers, the main resource used is host's CPU. Indeed, in the experiments carried out, CPU usage was observed with respect to the incoming traffic and we observed a linear relationship with the number of incoming packets, while the memory usage remained low around 5% in all cases.

Direct monitoring of CU-UP CPU usage is not sufficient, as it reflects the resource utilization caused by multiple DUs and their combined load, without providing details on the data volume contributed by each individual DU. This limitation can lead to ineffective scaling, particularly during scale in, as avoiding the assignment of DUs with loads that exceed the CU-UP's capacity is crucial. To address this and considering the linear relationship between CPU usage and the number of incoming packets, we developed a LR model tailored for each candidate host to predict CPU usage based on the number of incoming packets. In order for the controller to receive the incoming packet count, a custom monitoring API was developed and scheduled on each CU-UP node that communicates with the controller over HTTP. This custom monitoring tool collects the number of packets each CU-UP sends over the F1-U and forwards them to a central controller.

Contrary to typical scaling approaches used in other cloud-based applications, scaling 5G RAN components is not a straightforward procedure since all the services are stateful. As a result, standard tools such as the Kubernetes Pod Autoscaler do not function effectively in this context. Hence, the scaling process is not just about instance replication but instead creating new instances, correctly setting all the component's parameters and following the message schemes of the communication protocol among the scaled and non-scaled entities. To scale seamlessly and efficiently the CU-UP, the system should be able to support CU-UP Change messages [10], enabling each UE to change its assigned CU-UP without network deregistration. Although the CU-UP Change procedure is specified in 5G-NR Rel. 15, OAI has not yet implemented this procedure. To address this limitation, we designed a scaling mechanism that does not generate any faults to the network operation, by deploying an additional number of CU-UP instances and restarting the corresponding number of the UE instances in the scaling-out scenario. Regarding the scale-in scenario, we destroy the surplus CU-UP instances and immediately restart the corresponding UE instances to trigger reconnection with the 5G network. One limitation of our implementation is the interruption of the UE connection for a very short period of time due to the container restart, which can be considered acceptable, assuming the device remains connected to the network for extended periods and scaling events occur infrequently. The CU-UP Change procedure as described in [10] supports data forwarding from

the source gNB-CU-UP to the target gNB-CU-UP to ensure that there is no packet loss during the CU-UP switch. In order to avoid packet loss in our implementation, we monitor the UE connection state and generate traffic from/to the UE only if the UE is connected to the network. In real systems, all these network readjustments can be mitigated through the CU-UP Change mechanism with the data forwarding enabled.

The controller we developed dynamically scales out or in CU-UP instances according to their estimated CPU usage. In order to estimate the CPU Usage the LR model was implemented and trained for each candidate CU-UP node. Once trained, the model was saved and utilized as a pretrained model in the controller to predict CPU usage based on the number of processed packets. First, the controller receives the number of packets on the F1-U interfaces of the CU-UPs via our HTTP API, it aggregates the metric of total packets received per CU-UP and then estimates the total CPU Usage per CU-UP. The controller then implements the functionality of the algorithm illustrated in 1, according to which monitoring the estimated CPU usage and based on some predefined limits makes the decision whether the system should scale out, in or remain unchanged. Regarding the limits that we defined in this work, we set the upper and lower limits at 90% and 50%, respectively. These thresholds should ideally be chosen based on the specific requirements and characteristics of the system under operation. We selected the 90% threshold because performance degradation tends to occur when the CPU operates at such high utilization rates. The threshold 50%, on the other hand, was chosen to illustrate that when CPU utilization drops to half, it indicates sufficient capacity to merge two CU-UPs to optimize resource usage.

IV. EVALUATION

Extensive experiments were conducted to demonstrate the viability of the proposed design and approach. The same experiment was applied to both naive (non-scalable CU-UP) and CU-UP scalable support system, in order to examine the effectiveness of the proposed mechanism based on real-world dataset and demands of the clients. In both cases, we assume that users have the same pattern of transmission requirements. We also consider only DL for the metrics, as traffic over the UL does not significantly stress the CU-UP in our system.

A. Dataset

We used a real-world dataset extracted as detailed in [13], which presents a 5G trace collected from a major Irish mobile operator and offers two mobility patterns (static and car), and across two application patterns (video streaming and file download). Among these mobility and transmission patterns, we chose to employ the static pattern with a downloading application, since these had the largest transmission load requirements. The original dataset shows very sharp fluctuations between neighboring values, ranging from a few hundred Mbps to zero. To achieve a smoother dataset, we performed smoothing through a downsampling technique giving each point the maximum value of ten points on either side of it. This technique helps us to stress-test the CU-UP component

Fig. 2: Experimental Results Figures

TABLE I: Node Assignments and Specifications

Node	Components	CPU	Cores	RAM
1	NRF, UDR, UDM, AUSF, AMF, SMF, CU-CP, Controller	Intel Core Processor (Skylake, IBRS)	4	8GB
2,3,4	UPF (Slice: oai & slices & ims)	Intel Core Processor (Skylake, IBRS)	4	8GB
5,6	CU-UPs	Intel Core Processor (Skylake, IBRS)	4	8GB
7	DU, UE (Pair 1)	Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-8700 CPU @ 3.20GHz	6	16GB
8	DU, UE (Pair 2)	Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-8700 CPU @ 3.20GHz	6	16GB
9	DU, UE (Pair 3)	Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-8700 CPU @ 3.20GHz	6	16GB

under the most demanding DL conditions. Because the values of the dataset have a different range than those supported by our system, we applied min-max scaling to adjust the values to fall within the supported range. Subsequently, we isolated a segment of this dataset that stresses the CU-UP component, and creates desired conditions to scale out and in our system.

B. Experiments

In order to study the efficiency of the proposed system, we compare our solution to a system without support for any scaling. In both types of experiments, we use three clients.

Both the naive and the reactive scaling setup consist of a simple 5GCN architecture with the support of three UPFs to support the transmission needs of three clients. For the RAN part, we deploy the disaggregated RAN that follows the Option 2 split supporting the CP and UP separation at the RAN level. Each UE is connected to a different DU, so there is no drop in system performance due to another component overloading the 5G datapath except the CU-UP. Based on the above, the RAN consists of one CU-CP, one or multiple CU-UPs, according to the tested architectural scenario, and three

DUs. All the clients have the same traffic demands. We use a multiprocess python program to generate DL UDP traffic with the use of the *iperf3* application, running from the UPF N6 interface to each UE based on the values of the dataset. For the case of the naive 5G V-RAN network, we use one CU-UP, and for the case of the reactive network, the number of CU-UPs is determined by the integrated controller.

Figures 2a and 2d illustrate the transmitting pattern from the used dataset and the DL throughput received from a UE in the naive and the proposed scaling supported system accordingly. We present the results of one of the three UEs as an example since their behaviors are almost identical, with minimal differences among them. Figures 2g, 2h and 2i show the Euclidean distances of the incoming traffic values of each UE with their demand values in the case of the naive and scaling-enabled system. We used the Euclidean distance plot as it measures the system's ability to meet QoS requirements by quantifying demand-throughput gaps, whereas packet loss depends on implementation choices, often mitigated by large buffers at the cost of increased latency. Figures 2b and 2e show the real CPU utilization rates of the deployed CU-UP components, a single CU-UP in the first figure and the multiple CU-UPs in the second one. It is worth noting that when the utilization rate of a CU-UP is equal to zero, this CU-UP has not been deployed. As we observe, in the first transmission phase (0 - 206 sec), the client-requested traffic is insufficient to overload the CU-UP component.

In the second phase of the experiment (206-1026 sec), the CPU utilization of the single CU-UP exceeds the rate of 90%, which reveals an overload of the component and, therefore, in the scaling enabled system scale out is performed. During the scale out procedure, the clients that are registered to two out of the three configured slices are assigned to the same CU-UP, and the third slice to a different CU-UP, located on a different physical machine. In the naive system case, the overload of the CU-UP component is reflected in the 5G system's inability to satisfy the demands of its clients, as revealed in Figures 2a, where the UE receives less traffic than the desired one. The 5G system's inability happens due to the high CPU utilization during the second phase when the CPU reaches 100% of usage (Figure 2b). This is in contrast to the case of the scaling-enabled system where the UE receives a transmission speed very close to the desired one, as shown in Figure 2d since none of the deployed CU-UP reaches a high CPU Usage limit. The CU-UP serving the two slices results in higher CPU usage than the CU-UP serving one slice, which handles only one UE, as seen in Figure 2e. The inefficiency of the naive system is revealed, particularly in the graphs of Euclidean distance (Fig. 2g, 2h and 2i) and loss packets (Fig. 2c and 2f), whose values are much higher in the naive system. In the third phase of the experiments ($\approx 1000 - 1300$ sec), we observe a decrease in traffic see Figures 2a and 2d that implies a decrease in CPU utilization as observed in graphs 2b and 2e. No direct scale in is performed in the system due to the LR model, where the predictions do not create suitable conditions (estimated CPU usage to be less than 50%) for this

particular operation despite the reduced throughput. When this condition is met (1026 sec), scale in is performed, with one CU-UP adequately meeting the demands.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study we have implemented a real-world 5G V-RAN network, along with a mechanism to scale the CU-UP component of 5G RAN. The mechanism was designed based on the CPU Usage estimation, and tested using real-world data traffic. Thorough experiments validated the effectiveness of a dynamic scaling strategy for the CU-UP component. The experimental outcomes highlight the importance of this implementation since the reliability of the 5G V-RAN was enhanced as long as the system manages to satisfy User's QoS under dynamic and multiple network conditions. For the future, we aim to expose our system to even more dynamic network conditions and structure and solve an optimization problem taking into consideration the CU-UP placement in order to minimize the latency and maximize the throughput performance among the UE and the 5G network. We also plan to align our system with the O-RAN Radio Intelligent Controller (RIC) architecture by introducing a KPI that reports the number of data-transmitted packets per CU-UP, which will be sent to an xApp executing Algorithm 1 to manage CU-UP scaling decisions.

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